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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF EFFICACY OF CLUSTER AND
CONVENTIONAL IMMUNOTHERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH
ALLERGIC RHINITIS**Dr Seerat Fatima¹, Dr Beenish², Dr Rao Shahzad Ahmad³¹Mohi ud Din Islamic Medical College, Mirpur²Aziz Fatimah Medical & Dental College, Faisalabad³Medical Officer at DHQ Hospital, Rajanpur**Abstract:**

Introduction: Allergic rhinitis (AR) is an allergic disease mediated by IgE, which is increasing in incidence. **Aims and objectives:** The basic aim of the study is to analyse the efficacy of cluster and conventional immunotherapy in patients with allergic rhinitis. **Material and methods:** This cross sectional study was conducted in Mohi ud Din Islamic Medical College, Mirpur during January 2019 to July 2019. The data was collected from both male and female patients who visited the OPD of the hospital. All patients underwent a skin prick test (SPT) using histamine (positive control) and standard extracts. **Results:** The data was collected from 60 patients. Among the 60 patients enrolled in the present study, 57 completed follow-up: cluster immunotherapy group (n=28) and conventional immunotherapy group (n=29). Two out of the three cases lost to follow-up were from the cluster immunotherapy group, and the remaining case was from the conventional group. These results demonstrated that the effective rate after 6 months of treatment was less than that after 6 weeks in the cluster group. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that cluster immunotherapy is able to improve symptoms in patients with AR caused by dust mites, with no increase in adverse reactions. Therefore, cluster immunotherapy may be a rapid, effective, safe treatment for moderate to severe persistent AR.

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INTRODUCTION:

Allergic rhinitis (AR) is an allergic disease mediated by IgE, which is increasing in incidence. The important role of specific immunotherapy (SIT) and its mechanism, safety and effectiveness against disease progression have become better understood in recent years. The main advantage of SIT is its ability to alleviate clinical symptoms and reduce a patient's dependence on allergy medication [1]. SIT is the only therapy that can alter the natural course of allergic diseases through an immunoregulatory mechanism. In 2008, the World Health Organization's Allergic Rhinitis and its Impact on Asthma Workshop Group indicated that specific immunotherapy is used as the main therapy to treat AR.

The usual course of therapy with SIT includes subcutaneous immunotherapy (SCIT) and sublingual immunotherapy. SCIT treatment is administered for ~3 years and includes two phases: Dose accumulation and dose maintenance. SIT can be divided into conventional immunotherapy and cluster immunotherapy during the dose accumulation phase [2].

In conventional immunotherapy, the dose accumulation phase consists of injections of increasing doses of the allergen once a week, with the maintenance dose achieved after ~15 weeks. However, during the dose accumulation phase of cluster immunotherapy, the allergen is injected 2–3 times in 1 day each week, 30 min apart, thus the maintenance dose can be achieved within ~6 weeks. Therefore, the frequency of visits can be reduced and the maintenance dose is achieved quickly when using the cluster immunotherapy regimen [3].

Allergic rhinitis (AR) is mediated by immunoglobulin E (IgE) and a variety of immune cells and cytokines involved in inflammation of the nasal passages and is one of the most common otorhinolaryngological diseases [4]. The prevalence of AR has in recent years increased significantly, concomitant with industrialization and increasing levels of pollution in the environment. Although AR is not life-threatening, it has a marked effect on the quality of life of those afflicted and imposes an economic burden on society. This condition, if poorly controlled, can also increase the risk of asthma. Therefore, AR should be treated using effective modalities [5].

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study is to analyse the efficacy of cluster and conventional immunotherapy in patients with allergic rhinitis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Mohi ud Din Islamic Medical College, Mirpur during January 2019 to July 2019. The data was collected from both male and female patients who visited the OPD of the hospital. All patients underwent a skin prick test (SPT) using histamine (positive control) and standard extracts.

Data collection

Skin Prick Test was positive for the *Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus* dust mite allergen in all cases. Other inhaled allergens were all less than ++, including spring pollen, autumn pollen, polyvalent mold, polyvalent animal hair, polyvalent feather and cockroach. Specific IgE to serum dust mites were tested and all patients exhibited concentrations >0.7 KU/L. Patients were diagnosed with asthma after demonstrating airflow obstruction, with a peak expiratory flow of >70% demonstrated in all patients. All patients received standard vaccine immunotherapy against dust mite allergen. Each treatment course included a dose accumulation phase and a dose maintenance phase. During the dose accumulation phase, the initial dose in the conventional group was 20 SQ-U via one injection a week, which was escalated weekly until a maintenance dose of 100,000 SQ-U was achieved (12 weeks). This dose remained constant and the injection interval was extended to 6–8 weeks. In the cluster group, the initial dose was 10 SQ-U with 2–3 injections performed 30 min apart weekly.

Statistical analysis

SPSS 17.0 statistical software (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) was used to perform statistical analysis with χ^2 tests. $P < 0.05$ was considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 60 patients. Among the 60 patients enrolled in the present study, 57 completed follow-up: cluster immunotherapy group (n=28) and conventional immunotherapy group (n=29). Two out of the three cases lost to follow-up were from the cluster immunotherapy group, and the remaining case was from the conventional group. These results demonstrated that the effective rate after 6 months of treatment was less than that after 6 weeks in the cluster group. Many patients exhibited an improvement in symptoms; however, this effect was reduced with more injections. Conversely, the effective rate in the conventional group increased from 51.72% after 6 weeks of treatment to 75.86% after 6 months of treatment.

Table 01: Comparison of clinical efficacy after 6 weeks of treatment.

Group	Obviously effective	Effective	No effect	Total	Efficiency (%)
Cluster	14	10	4	28	85.71 ^a
Conventional	8	7	14	29	51.72
Total	22	17	18	57	68.42

^aP<0.01 vs. the conventional group.

Table 02: Comparison of clinical efficacy after 1 year of treatment.

Group	Obviously effective	Effective	No effect	Total	Efficiency (%)
Cluster	13	9	6	28	78.57 ^a
Conventional	12	10	7	29	75.86
Total	25	19	13	57	77.19

^aP>0.05 vs. the conventional group.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, we compared the efficacy of the buildup phase of conventional and cluster immunotherapies in both adults and children. When evaluating the effectiveness of immunotherapy, the common and optimal parameters representing efficacy are reductions in symptoms and/or drug intake [6]. In our study, we evaluated the effectiveness of immunotherapy through skin prick tests and symptom scores. The results indicated that, upon completion of the buildup phase of immunotherapy, whether using the conventional or accelerated cluster schedule, the symptom scores of the patients for the most part decreased significantly, which is consistent with the results of an earlier study [7].

Immunotherapy is only defined as clinically significant when a patient's symptom grade is reduced by >30%. According to this criterion, in 57 patients with AR, after 1 year's treatment the total effective rate was 77.2%, which is similar to the 75.0% reported by Chang and Hong when treating AR through immunotherapy [8]. The majority of patients are allergic to both house dust mites and dust mites, since they possess similar allergenicity, and this may be one reason for the good effect demonstrated in the present patients. The two treatment regimens exhibited substantial effects after 6 weeks, with the cluster group demonstrating a more obvious effect than the conventional group [9]. Although the exact mechanism of this effect remains unknown, the treatment effect after 6 months demonstrated in the present study was satisfying and clinically meaningful. The WHO recommends that immunotherapy should last for at least 3 years; however, the present patients were only observed for 1 year. Therefore, further clinical observation is required to assess the long-term effects of these two treatment regimens [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that cluster immunotherapy is able to improve symptoms in patients with AR caused by dust mites, with no increase in adverse reactions. Therefore, cluster immunotherapy may be a rapid,

effective, safe treatment for moderate to severe persistent AR.

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